

Lessons learnt from non-aviation sector noise management best practices: The ANIMA project results

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Abstract

Noise affecting citizens and communities is a growing problem, recent figures provided by the European Commission actually highlight that almost 80 million people are estimated to be exposed to road noise ≥ 55 dB over the whole day, followed by over 10 million exposed to rail noise. Within the H2020 project ANIMA a specific analysis has been carried out to consider prevailing sources of environmental noise that go beyond the aviation sector and how noise related to non-aviation sectors can affect local communities.

The main objective of this exercise is to identify what aviation can learn for strategies of reducing community responses to noise from other sectors. For this, this paper reports on the following key specific non-aviation sectors: 1) Transport, mainly roads and railways; 2) Construction; 3) Wind turbines/parks; and 4) Domestic and leisure activities in over ten different case studies.

For each sector, a comparative analysis of similarities and differences between the other sector and aviation noise has been provided, this has been followed by an in-depth study of over 10 case studies across the other sector noise spectrum covering a global remit, from Europe as well as internationally, highlighting lessons learned and potentially some transferable noise mitigation strategies.

Keywords: environmental noise annoyance; noise abatement strategies; transferability; communities; aviation; case studies.

1. Introduction

Community noise is a growing problem in our fast-paced and increasingly congested world. Noise sources, especially in urban areas, are closer than ever to residential areas and other sensitive land uses. Chronic or long-term noise exposure can cause severe annoyance and disturbance to people's daily lives and be harmful for human's health.

The following document considers and discuss noise from non-aviation sectors, exploring noise monitoring and modelling techniques, how noise may impact on communities living near to sources of (non-aviation) noise and how impacts/noise exposure is communicated to those communities.

Noise mitigation and reduction strategies are also discussed with specific reference to case study examples and other relevant literature/research. Key messages from this study are also presented and discussed, along with suggested noise mitigation/reduction strategies that may be transferable to the aviation sector.

Other than aviation, roads, rail and industry (e.g. construction, wind farms, etc.) are considered to be the main sources of noise that impact on communities across Europe (and the rest of the developed world). By way of example, Figure 1 shows for the 33 member countries of the European Environment Agency (EEA-33) the estimated number of people exposed to average noise levels ≥ 55 dB (expressed as the L_{den}^1). Those numbers are based on the most recent country submissions and redeliveries of the 2017 round of noise reporting.

¹ L_{den} (day-evening-night, using EU time periods) noise level. It is a descriptor of noise level based on energy equivalent noise level (L_{eq}) over a whole day with a penalty of 10 dB(A) for night-time noise (23.00-7.00) and an additional penalty of 5 dB(A) for evening noise (i.e. 19.00-23.00).

Both inside and outside of urban areas, roads are the dominant source of noise affecting communities, followed by railways and, to a much lesser extent, airports and industry. In the urban environment, almost 80 million people in the EEA-33 are estimated to be exposed to road noise ≥ 55 dB (Lden).

Interestingly, when comparing major infrastructure (green bars in Figure 1) with overall sector (blue bars in Figure 1), major railways account for nearly 50% of the population exposed to $L_{den} \geq 55$ dB. This is similar to the case of major airports which account for 45% of the population assessed to be exposed for the all Airport sector. Finally, for roads only 27% of the population is exposed to $L_{den} \geq 55$ dB when considering major roads only, this is expected since the major roads network traditionally represents a small percentage of the total road network and are situated mainly outside urban areas with urban roads accounting for the majority of the residential population exposed.

However, when we focus on the annoyance, although fewer people are exposed to air traffic noise than that from road or rail as indicated in the above Figure 1, it is reported to cause greater annoyance (Guarini et al., 2012; ISO, 2016; Münzel et al., 2014).

Noise annoyance across modes can present substantial differences. The curves in Figure 2 represent the probability of highly annoyed adults exposed to a level of noise expressed in Lden.

For rail, road and aircraft the curves were derived for adults on the basis of several surveys (26 for aircraft noise, 19 for road noise, and 8 for railways noise) conducted across 11 countries (EC, 2017). Those curves have been integrated by the authors adding results of a Dutch study on industry and wind turbine noise, the results are presented in Figure 2.

2. Methodology

This paper focuses on the review of several practices for noise mitigation and reduction strategies best practices related to non-aviation sources of environmental noise.

In order to achieve that, three main steps have been followed:

1. The first was to explore and review what characterises and defines the most important non-aviation sectors, affecting local communities.
2. The second, a review of the different noise monitoring and modelling techniques across the different non-aviation sectors has been carried out to understand if commonalities between different sectors exist and how that can help in defining the mitigation and reduction strategies for the aviation sector.
3. Finally, a number of case studies have been presented and interviews with stakeholders were carried out to gather key and detailed information about the mitigation and reduction strategies, as well as the role of community engagement in each case study and how that has played a role in the success of the strategy implementation.

As a result of the different case study analyses, key messages and transferability to the aviation sector and other work packages in the Horizon 2020 funded EU research project ANIMA (Aviation Noise Impact Management through novel Approaches) have been considered and presented in a separate section of this paper.

Fig 1. EEA-33 — Number of people exposed to average day-evening-night noise levels ($L_{den} \geq 55$ dB) [EEA, 2017]

Fig. 2. Percentage of people highly annoyed within the exposed group across different sectors, aircraft, road, rail, industry and wind turbine noise.

Since ANIMA is a Research and Innovation project, a dedicated section has been included in the conclusions, focussing on future steps and gaps that have been identified in order to suggest and propose new research activities and the main focus for future research.

3. Similarities and differences with aviation noise

Since this paper focuses on the opportunity to learn from the experience of noise reduction strategies from other sectors, below are reported the key elements of similarity and difference between the noise generated from the other sectors and the aviation noise.

Table 1. Similarities and differences between other sector noise and aviation noise.

Sector	Similarities	Differences
Transportation - Road	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transportation-derived noise - Local impact - Emotive subject - Policies dominated by average noise (Lden, Lnight) - Discrete events also important (night-time operations, secondary roads) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Little community engagement - Fewer protests - Complaints towards State - Multiple sources (tyres, engines) - More constant noise (daytime, main roads) - Community can have stake in noise source
Transportation - Rail	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transportation noise - Discrete events - Predictable - Sector expected to cause more future disturbances due to economic growth 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Little community engagement - Less number of complaints - Perceived as beneficial, accessible - Complaints toward State - Blame with operator - Impact across large area - Phase of technological development - More constant noise event - Vibrations more relevant with rail - Opinion on environmental friendliness of transportation means - High pitched, sudden wheel and brake squealing noise
Wind turbines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Predominantly aerodynamic noise - Established community engagement process - Vocal and organized opposition - Uncertainty about future noise impact - Emotional debate - Local impact - Governed by average noise loads (Lden) - Night-time disturbance is relevant 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - (semi-) constant noise source - Difference in annoyance with respect to sound character - Strong visual component (in addition to noise) - Public is generally favourable towards wind energy, yet against nearby wind turbines (Not In My Back Yard, NIMBY) - Community can have stake in noise source
Construction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Discrete events - Community engagement process - Local impact - Emotional debate - Governed by average noise (Lden) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shorter duration (known end) - Non-transportation noise - Strong visual component - Complaints toward builder/contractor
Domestic and Leisure Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Occurs suddenly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Noise is often generated by sources or individuals personally known to the receiver - Noises often carry information (i.e. spoken word, music with lyrics etc.) - Occurrence in closest spatial proximity to the receiver - High potential to cause controversies in a community - No community engagement - Legal consequences can result immediately

4. Monitoring

The direct measurement (or monitoring) of noise at (usually noise sensitive) locations is a key aspect of environmental noise assessment, and is usually the first step in establishing ‘baseline’ conditions before further detailed assessment/modelling of the potential noise impact of new infrastructure (e.g. wind turbine/park) is undertaken.

Noise measurement/monitoring can also be used to assess, either in-situ or under controlled/research conditions, the efficacy of physical noise mitigation measures, such as acoustic balconies or barriers to protect residents from, for example, road and rail noise in built-up urban environments.

Noise measurement/monitoring is also often used to assess the impact of **construction** noise, and specifically to assess compliance with specified noise limits applicable at the site boundary or at noise sensitive receptors (e.g. residential dwellings) near the construction site. ‘Live’ measurement data feeds can be used by site operatives to modify or stop certain activities if noise limits are near to, or are, being breached.

Noise measurement/monitoring can be used by relevant local authorities to investigate and help resolve noise complaints from individuals or communities affected by **domestic and leisure sources** (such as noisy residential dwellings, bars, restaurants, night clubs etc.).

Leisure noises ideally should be measured at different locations, to give immediate noise control as well as a more realistic overview of noise propagation for single events.

However, there is an experimental approach to monitoring larger areas with an Internet-of-Things approach. As part of the Horizon 2020 program MONICA, it was tested to monitor the noise levels of parts of a city (pilot cities were Copenhagen, Leeds, Lyon, Turin, Bonn and Hamburg) by building a network of low-cost smartphones equipped with an application (“OpeNoise”) (Gallo et al., 2018).

In terms of **railway** noise and its propagation throughout an area, many situational factors have to be taken into consideration. The most decisive levels of analysis for railway are: Kind of train; Composition of the train (what locomotive is pulling what sort of wagons and how many wagons does it pull); Kind of wheels; Physical condition of the tracks (“rail roughness”); Kind and condition of the brakes; Speed at what it travels at a given time and place; Geographical setting of the area through which it travels.

Given this variety of different requirements, railway noise is mostly calculated. This means, the relevant parameters are assessed and fed into a calculation program that is able to give an estimate about the sound propagation along a track. The EU (EC, 2014) has given out Limit pass by noises at 7.5 meters from the middle of the track and in 1.2 meters height for different rolling-stock-subsystems that are not be exceeded

If the measurements are to be made over a short period (such as boundary monitoring around a **construction** site which is a subject to short-term, intense periods of noise generation), a handheld sound level meter may be suitable. If the measurements need to be made over a longer period (for example to assess the long-term noise exposure of a residential dwelling subject to wind turbine/park noise), an outdoor environmental measurement system may be needed.

Technical committee 88 of the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) prepares standards that deal with, among others, measurement techniques for wind turbines. Modern monitoring systems detail appropriate noise measurement techniques, including hardware, procedures, data requirements and reporting requirements. One of the requirements is the measurement between wind speeds of 6 m/s and 10 m/s.

5. Mapping and Modelling

This section provides an overview of noise modelling and mapping process, indicating different approaches to designing noise maps, from transport sector or other noise sources (industry, construction, etc.), aiming at identifying examples to be taken on board by aviation sector.

5.1. Noise Mapping

A Noise Map is a map of an area which is ‘coloured’ according to the noise levels in the area. Sometimes the noise levels may be shown by contour lines which show the boundaries between different noise levels in an area. Several datasets and tools are involved designing noise maps.

As part of the review process a good example of noise mapping guidance has been identified, in one proposed by the Environmental Protection Agency of Ireland who produced guidance on strategic noise mapping to support requirements detailed in the Environmental Noise Regulations 2006². This provides a simple and useful representation as a step-by-step process. The guidance assists designated Noise Mapping Bodies (NMBs) in carrying out their duties under the 2006 Regulations, including making and approving strategic noise maps for agglomerations, roads, railways, major industrial sites and aircraft using airports. The guidance also covers the reporting of strategic noise maps and how they are presented to the public.

²<http://www.epa.ie/pubs/advice/noisemapping/epaguidancenoteforstrategicnoisemapping.html>

The main structure of the guidance is to present a staged approach to deliver strategic noise mapping. The approach set out may be summarised as a seven-stage process, as shown in Figure 3 below.

Fig. 3. Overview of noise mapping process

The strategic noise mapping process includes two key inputs:

- Base model definition (including digital ground model, buildings, topography and barriers); and
- Source model/parameter definition (for road, rail, industry, aircraft).

Once the base model and source model/parameters are defined, noise modelling is undertaken, with careful consideration given to the overall model uncertainty and the user defined calculation settings adopted for the model. The importance of pre- and post-modelling data checks is emphasised. Post-processing of the model outputs in terms of the spatial resolution/receptor resolution (area, population, dwelling) is discussed in the guidance, along with how the modelling/mapping process and results should be presented to the regulator and the wider public.

5.2. Noise Modelling

In 2004, AEA Technology Rail BV published a ‘state of the art’ technical document on noise modelling and mapping in support of the European project IMAGINE (Improved Methods for the Assessment of the Generic Impact of Noise in the Environment) (IMAGINE, 2004). In relation to noise modelling/computation methods, different methodologies are discussed and compared for road, rail, air, industrial and leisure & domestic sources. For the purpose of strategic noise mapping as required by Article 7 of the European Environmental Noise Directive (Directive 2002/49/EC; in short: END)³ the European Commission developed the Common Noise Assessment Methods to be adopted and used by EU member states (CNOSSOS-EU)⁴. Since January 2019 the EU member states have to transpose CNOSSOS in their national legislation⁵. However, for national purposes in noise policy of European countries (noise remediation and prevention) beyond noise mapping and action planning according to the END national noise calculation models exist beside CNOSSOS-EU, as well as models derived from research projects such as the above mentioned IMAGINE or the associated project HARMONOISE (Harmonised Accurate and Reliable Methods for the EU Directive on the Assessment and Management of Environmental Noise; van Maercke, & Defrance, 2007). The following sections refer to these models.

5.2.1. Transportation - Roads

In relation to the computation of road noise, the main models are from six European nations: Austrian RVS 3.02; French NMPB; German RLS-90; Dutch RMV II; Nordic Nord 2000; and UK CRTN.

Noise modelling software and associated methodologies are well developed, particularly with respect to roads. The UK Department for Transport’s (DfT) Calculation of Road Traffic Noise guidance (CRTN, 1988) outlines a methodology for predicting noise levels at different distances from a highway based on traffic characteristics (e.g. vehicle speeds and traffic composition), intervening ground cover and road configuration etc.

CRTN has also been implemented as an optional noise calculation method in leading proprietary noise modelling

³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32002L0049&from=EN>

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/reference-reports/common-noise-assessment-methods-europe-cnosos-eu>

⁵ Directive 2015/996; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32015L0996&from=EN>

software packages such as SoundPLAN (<https://soundplan-uk.com/>) and CadnaA (<https://www.datakustik.com/products/cadnaa/cadnaa/>).

5.2.2. *Transportation - Rail*

Like for road traffic there is noise modelling software available for railways. However, HARMONOISE doesn't offer a method for calculating railway noises, which is only available with the IMAGINE software

Taking as an example, in the HARMONOISE / IMAGINE model, rolling noise is split into the vehicle and track contribution. In addition, the rail model takes into account all other potential noise sources, such as traction elements (exhaust, fans, and compressors), braking noise (including brake squeal), curve squeal and aerodynamic noise. The level of detail of these extra sources is significantly greater than is the case with other available mapping models. National railway noise models in use are implemented in standard software such as SoundPLAN or CadnaA.

5.2.3. *Construction*

Noise modelling has also been used successfully for large-scale construction projects, enabling the iterative calculation of noise impacts at sensitive receptors based on different site plant configurations, operating times and new and updated source noise data for key items of plant. This iterative modelling approach enables the construction contractor to demonstrate to the local authority that, despite the flexibility required in operational activities and scheduling to meet project milestones, no significant adverse impacts on local businesses and residents would occur. In another example, from Addiscombe Environmental Consultants Limited (<http://www.aecl.co.uk/services/construction-noise>), construction noise calculations can be undertaken using in-house modelling capabilities. It allows possible mitigation options to be assessed prior to commencement of on-site activity.

5.2.4. *Industry - wind turbine*

Predicting wind turbine noise is essential for the design of more quiet turbines and for assessing the noise impact around wind parks. Several approaches exist that range from 'rule-of-thumb' methods to full-on computational fluid dynamics (CFD) methods. In between are hybrid semi-empirical methods.

The rule-of-thumb methods can provide an order of magnitude assessment of noise, but fail to address the impact of design changes. CFD computations are very accurate, but are usually time intensive and thus costly for a calculating the 3D flow around a wind turbine. A hybrid approach assessing different sources separately using finite-element methods (instead of resolving the entire system) currently represent the state-of-art (Oerlemans, 2011).

5.2.5. *Leisure & Domestic*

This document focuses on the review of existing literature and although the authors have carried out a comprehensive review, an official procedure to model leisure and/or domestic noise seems not to be available. This is probably due to the fact that domestic and leisure noise is the result of a combination of two or more of the other noise sources, and only occasionally they relate to a single event (like a concert in an open environment or a big sports event for example).

6. **Case studies, role of community engagement and lessons learnt**

6.1. *Transportation - Road*

Roads are the dominant sources of noise affecting communities in Western Europe. Road traffic noise is caused by vehicle engines, tyre-road interactions and vehicle-air interactions. Vehicle speed, traffic composition, driver behaviour and road surface composition and integrity are all important factors determining the level of noise emitted from roads. Unlike in the aviation sector, where discrete noise events (such as aircraft taking off and landing) are dominant, road noise tends to be more constant in nature (especially during the day time on strategic roads). Road noise tends to have a localised impact and can elicit an emotive response from those that live or work near to busy roads. Planned new roads or long-term traffic management schemes that redirect traffic into otherwise unaffected locations can result in a significant localised resistance/protest (often directed at the local authority/highways authority). Noise associated with new airports or significant airport extensions tends to result in national-level media coverage with associated discontent directed towards the national government/state.

Community Engagement: The specific response of individuals within a given community to road noise can vary considerably due to some non-acoustical factors such as, age, sex and socio-economic status (demographic factors), general noise sensitivity, attitudes towards the source or towards authorities (dispositional and attitudinal factors), and the amount of time spent at home, or the visibility of the noise source (situational factors). Numerous studies have investigated the effects of community noise and the noise exposure dose-response of individuals. Active engagement and ongoing and effective communication with local populations that are near to sources of community noise is now considered to be critical (and indeed best practice) in managing noise impacts/exposure.

Mitigation and Reduction Strategies: Numerous noise mitigation/reduction techniques for road sources are detailed in the literature. These measures can generally be categorised as those that can be applied at source, those that can modify/disrupt the noise propagation pathway, and those that can be applied at the receptor. These measures can be applied in isolation or as part of a multi-functional noise reduction strategy/design. The following are the most

common approaches (Low-noise surfaces; Low-noise tyres; Electric/hybrid vehicles; influence driver behaviour; better/improved junction design; Traffic improvement schemes; Noise barriers and Façade insulation).

Case Study and lessons learnt: Hong Kong is well known for its high rise, high density urban environment. It is often necessary for new housing developments, including public housing, to be built next to heavily trafficked and congested roads. Four specific receptor-based innovative noise mitigation solutions for the public housing to protect residents from road traffic/surface transport noise were considered and assessed by the Hong Kong Housing Authority – namely modular apartment design, acoustic windows, acoustic balconies and enhanced acoustic balconies. Noise reductions for the modular apartment design, acoustic windows and acoustic balconies are estimated to range between 3 dB(A) and 8 dB(A) in terms of Leq. Enhanced acoustic balconies are likely to achieve a noise reduction closer to 10 dB(A) Leq. These noise attenuation methods are important in highly constrained environments where surface transport is a key component of the noise environment. Key lessons learnt are:

- Roads are the dominant sources of noise affecting communities in Western Europe. Vehicle speed, traffic composition, driver behaviour and road surface composition and integrity are all important factors determining the level of noise emitted from roads.
- The calculation/modelling of road noise is widely undertaken in Europe. For example, the UK's CTRN methodology has been incorporated into proprietary noise modelling software packages.
- Numerous mitigation measures for controlling road noise are detailed in the literature. Measures aimed at controlling noise at source are more effective than those aimed at modulating the propagation pathway or directly protecting the receptor.
- Case study from Hong Kong indicates that receptor-based mitigation can be effective and is important in densely populated and spatially confined environments where options for source - or pathway-based mitigation options are limited.

6.2. *Transportation - Rail*

With road traffic being the biggest sector for noise complaints, railways come in second regarding the noise impact on communities. Although train speeds and driver behaviour are strictly limited by regulations and schedules they run on, there are various other factors besides the speed a train drives at that affect the noise emissions, which are mostly found in geographical and track related components.

Like road traffic however, railway noise is relatively constant, except for the characteristic brake squeal and the heavy vibration that go along with a train passing by. If the train is pulled by a diesel locomotive, there is also a high level of engine noise involved.

For decades, the railways have had a much better image in terms of noise perception, the best of all of the mentioned noise sources in this paper, the reason is, it is believed to have been recognised as the most environmentally friendly mode of transport. As a result, the public opposition, compared to aviation and road traffic, seems to be smaller in total numbers. However, in specific, high exposed regions (e.g. in communities along the Rotterdam – Genoa corridor such as those in the Middle-Rhine Valley) the complaints and oppositional activities are as strong as those in airport regions, probably due to the increase of freight rail traffic over time, in particular in evening and night time. Recent evidence on railway noise effects indicate a decrease if not disappearance of the advantage of the railway compared to road traffic with regard to adverse noise responses (WHO, 2018).

Community engagement: Rail companies have manifested attention towards community engagement and communication tools. As an example, a big truck drives through all of Germany to showcase the impact of noise mitigation interventions to the public using VR simulation. Additionally, in all major construction projects there are dialogue forums that do involve community members along with railway staff.

Mitigation and Reduction Strategies: Regarding the overall noise mitigation a so-called system approach is taken that enables to take the whole system into account:

- The vehicle, with the wheel, the brakes, the bogie or axle and the vehicle body, all connected by springs and dampers (Train design; Friction modifiers; Brake technology; Depots)
- The track, with basic elements the rail, the rail fixation with rail pads, the sleeper, the ballast and the sub-soil (Shunting Yards; Steel Bridges; Vibration)
- Noise barriers and Façade insulation

Case Studies and lessons learnt: The case studies highlight the interaction between noise mitigation interventions and communication. The main case study involved VR simulation to show the effects of a new type of brakes that can be retrofitted to conventional rolling stock. The measure drastically reduces rolling noise from existing material without the need for an expensive overhaul of the braking system. The simulations created awareness and enthusiasm among rail professionals to reduce the primary source of railway noise from existing rolling stock.

The takeaway lesson here is that communication and education can help to support a holistic noise management and even have an effect on their own. Key lessons learnt are:

- trains have been perceived as publicly useful and environmentally friendly for a longer time. However, they are noisy and cause major disturbances in their proximity at both, high and low speeds
- vibration is a considerable issue with trains

- there are a lot of noise mitigation strategies that are applicable at the train, at the track or at the surrounding environment.
- railway companies apply communication and community involvement strategies
- the case studies illustrate the success of communication efforts

6.3. Construction

Construction sites can generate significant, but often relatively short-term, levels of noise that can disturb residents in their homes and other noise sensitive receptors (e.g. offices). Construction sites are inherently noisy, and often involve unavoidable activities such as piling, demolition and the use of pneumatic equipment, all of which can lead to excessive levels of noise on site. A balancing act between the needs of the developer to carry out necessary works and the rights of neighbours to enjoy their properties (or place of work) is required.

Community Engagement: Active engagement and ongoing and effective communication with local populations that are near to construction sites is now considered to be critical (and indeed best practice) in managing noise impacts/exposure. In London, good practice guidance on noise control for construction and demolition sites has been published and recommends that a community liaison plan and a complaints procedure is developed for all construction sites, regardless of the size/complexity/noise risk of the project. The same guidance also recommends, depending on the (noise) risk of the site, regular meetings with the local community and regulator, newsletters and email communications with the local community, and the development of project-specific websites to share information about the construction project and any noise issues.

Mitigation and Reduction Strategies: Construction noise can be managed by using a combination of mitigation measures designed to control noise at source (including how the site is managed and how equipment is used and maintained) and those designed to control the propagation of noise from site (for example the use of screens or bunds). In terms of controlling noise at source, there are many general measures that can be applied at all construction sites, including:

- Avoiding unnecessary revving of engines and switching off equipment when not required.
- Keeping internal haul routes well maintained and avoiding steep gradients.
- Use of rubber linings in, for example, chutes and dumpers to reduce impact noise.
- Minimising the drop height of materials.
- Starting plant and vehicle engines sequentially rather than all together.

In relation to controlling the propagation of construction noise, increasing the distance between the noise source and noise sensitive receptor(s) and the installation of bunds, screens and barriers can all help modulate the propagation of noise from construction sites.

Case Studies and lessons learnt: For a flood/water barrier construction project in Lincolnshire, UK, a Construction and Noise and Vibration Management Plan was imposed as part of the planning approval for the scheme. The Plan states that Best Practicable Means (BPM) of noise control will be applied during construction works to minimise noise at neighbouring residential properties and other sensitive receptors arising from construction activities. General principles of noise management are outlined in the plan, including measures for controlling noise at source and more generally across the site through administrative and legal controls, control of working hours etc. Specific noise control measures for particular activities are also detailed in the Plan. For a Crossrail station/ticket hall construction project in central London, the use of noise modelling/prediction, compliance monitoring and effective community liaison were also key success factors for the construction project. Key lessons learnt are:

- Construction sites can generate significant, but often relatively short-term, levels of noise.
- Construction noise tends to have a localised impact, with any complaints usually directed to the local authority or construction contractor.
- Balancing act between the needs of the developer to carry out necessary works and the rights of neighbours to enjoy their properties (or place of work) is required.
- Monitoring and modelling of construction noise is quite commonplace, especially for large and complex construction projects.
- Active and ongoing community engagement is important in communicating and managing noise impacts/risks of construction sites.
- Mitigation measures are well understood and range from those that are applicable at source to those that modulate the noise propagation path. There are several general mitigation measures that can be applied at all construction sites.
- Case studies from the UK emphasise the importance of the regulatory framework in securing effective mitigation. Noise modelling, monitoring and community engagement were key elements of successful construction noise management.

6.4. Industry (Wind Energy)

Wind energy is a key component in the energy transition from fossil fuels to renewable and sustainable energy sources. In order to reach climate goals for 2020, 2030 and 2050, large scale developments of on- and offshore wind parks are planned throughout Europe.

Onshore wind turbines potentially expose citizens to noise, shadow flicker and affect the natural landscape. Therefore, plans for new wind parks can face significant opposition.

Community Engagement: While people are generally favourable towards green energy, local communities fear wind turbines due to noise, visual pollution or a negative impact on property values. Plans for new wind parks come with environmental impact assessments that quantify the impact of the wind park in terms of noise, third party risk and shadow flickering. People are then allowed to comment and oppose the plans. If the plans are within norms, the construction can commence. Opposition to wind parks can result in protests, lawsuits and project delay. To prevent high costs, delay and political interference, developers of wind parks try to build support for their plans by proactively informing residents of the plans, addressing concerns and involving them in design changes (such as the layout of the wind park).

Mitigation and Reduction Strategies: Similar to aviation, wind turbine noise reduction relies on the reduction of noise at the source, land use planning and operational restrictions.

Both adaptation of the blade geometry and addition of serrations can reduce the noise by 4 dB.

Noise limits are set on national level and often distinguish between the type of location (rural, urban), time of day and wind conditions. In addition to noise limits, wind parks are limited by third party risk and shadow flickering constraints. No houses are allowed within these limits. Regarding shadow flickering, residents sometimes have the ability to (temporarily) shut down a nearby wind turbine if shadow flickering occurs.

Case Studies and lessons learnt: The case studies review the development of two wind parks in The Netherlands: One to replace an existing wind park, the other entirely new. The two studies highlight the possible differences in public reaction to wind energy. Both cases included a proactive community campaign. However, the timing of the participation process, the familiarity with wind energy and the responsibility for project coordination led to different responses. Although based on a sample size of only two, it appears that a locally coordinated engagement process initiated at the start of the project that allows community input on turbine location for residents who are already exposed to wind turbines, leads to more favourable results. What might be surprising is the potential impact of 'local history' that can fuel opposition to developments beyond reason when not addressed. Key lessons learnt are:

- The engagement process should start as soon as possible when there are still design choices to be made.
- Local support can be increased by involving communities in the decision making process, either by asking for their input or be clearly explaining the rationale behind the design choices.
- Visual aids can help the community build an understanding of the impact of the plans on their local environment. It can be highly favourable to create and communicate a tangible benefit to those affected by the developments, e.g. participation via an energy cooperation or an energy discount.
- Finally, the local element is also important when it comes to decision making. Remote decision making might lead to alienation and distrust, especially when local history and existing tensions are ignored.

6.5. Domestic & Leisure Noise

Domestic and Leisure noises are not a category like the others treated in this paper. Due to the lack of a definition, most type of noise/activities that intuitively fall into that category are not scientifically recognized. Most domestic and leisure noise issues are treated as single events, that happen randomly and only over a short period of time, e.g. a neighbour moving his lawn, a dog barking, or even a concert that happens once a year, but only for a couple of hours or in some specific days. Accordingly, abatement practices in this sector are handled differently from the others.

Community Engagement: There are not many community engagement interventions to be found in regards to domestic and leisure noise management. For some exceptions, people are informed about particularly noisy activities that may endure over a couple of hours or days. Mostly, people are advised to act on their own when it comes to the aforementioned disturbances. There are examples of leaflets being distributed to teach residents on their own how to act in cases of noise being generated in their living environment.

Mitigation and Reduction Strategies: As stated above, domestic and leisure noise interventions are mostly complaint driven and due to their temporal character, the management mostly involves complaint management. However, there are technical solutions available that are applicable at home. Active and passive noise control devices and constructions may not be targeted towards any specific domestic or leisure noise source, but are effective in sound proofing people's living environment. The further treatment of complaints, the restriction of hours, the insulation of buildings and spaces and the immediate reaction to the infringement of community noise guidelines are the only cases of domestic and leisure noise mitigation or intervention that are steadily executed, according to the examples visited.

Case Study and lessons learnt: The presented case studies show a couple of the mentioned interventions. Most of them however do not report an adequate noise monitoring activity or a full detailed report. Most methods seem to be superficial and cannot compete with the results and findings from the other sectors. A competent evaluation of noise mitigation is mostly left out and the assumption that due to a lack of complaints, residents are not annoyed is question-worthy to say the least. The case study from Hong Kong showed, that basic noise insulation can be done with rudimentary tools and the case study by Marchuk and Henry (2016) illustrated, what can be done within the scope of soundproofing to realize both a pleasant nightlife and undisturbed living. Key lessons learnt are:

- Domestic and leisure noise is the most disregarded sector by science and authorities

- There is no lobby or representation of interest
- Domestic and leisure noises are mostly being treated as a collection of the other noise sectors and are not clearly defined
- Mostly complaint management and immediate actions are applied to resolve conflicts due to noise annoyance.

7. Discussion on transferability and Conclusions

The set of non-aviation sectors analysed and presented in this paper provides a range of different noise sources and problems which, in some cases, are broadly comparable to the sources and problems apparent in the aviation sector. However, the case studies and noise mitigation strategies discussed in this paper, also indicate that there are some lessons that can be learnt and some elements that are potentially transferable to the aviation sector.

In all sectors, measures of noise control at the source are most effective but not always possible to implement. Mitigation measures that modify or disrupt the noise propagation pathway can partly be adopted in aviation when referring to the construction of the infrastructure. For example, constructions of bypasses in the road sector in order to relieve residential areas could be transferred to the aviation sector in terms of a shift of flight paths.

Examples from the road sector (case study Hong-Kong) and as discussed for the noise sources neighbourhood and leisure (insulation, active and passive noise cancellation) indicate that measures at the receptor can sometimes be effective for densely populated environments where options for source or pathway-based mitigation options are limited. However, caution is advised when concluding to prioritise these receptor-based measures against the others as they limit the noise abatement mainly to the indoor situation.

From almost all sectors considered in this paper aviation can learn that non-acoustical factors such as attitudes towards the source and towards authorities and the situational context (e.g. visibility of the source, time spent at home) contribute to the community responses to noise. Partly and in line with technical/acoustical improvements these contextual factors can be used to further reduce adverse noise effects and to improve residents' quality of life.

The time of day residents spent at home is one of the crucial situational factors. What aviation can learn from other sectors is that managing the traffic over the course of day should at best be socially accepted. This might lead in part to partial time-dependent traffic restrictions; at least, if possible, it would be desirable to negotiate this with the affected communities. Other situational (context) factors refer to the visibility of the source and – in a broader sense – the design of the residential environment. If a new residential area or single house is planned in a community, with the orientation of the residential building the visibility of the (existing or anticipated) noise source (e.g. to the flight path) can be modified and a quiet façade be created. In line with this, other factors, not mentioned above, e.g. the access to green areas or creation of positive sounds (soundscape), can be taken into account as this is also known to reduce adverse noise effects (Van Kamp et al., 2019).

With regard to the non-acoustical attitudinal contributors of community responses to noise they are best addressed by measures of community engagement and communication tools. In almost all sectors examples were identified that indicate that these measures can be successful in minimising adverse noise effects together with technical/acoustical measures. Examples from the different sectors like VR simulations showcasing the impact of noise interventions, project-specific websites, newsletters, e-mail communications, meetings, dialogue forum, community liaison, involvement of communities in the decision making process show the range of communication with and participation of communities from uni-directional information to bi-directional interactive engagement in which concerns of different parties are addressed. In principle, all these activities are possible in airport regions with regard the management of aircraft noise. In addition, the Dutch case studies on wind turbine constructions indicate that sharing the economic benefit generated by an infrastructure in addition to noise abatement measures would support minimising the adverse health effects. In the aviation sector this would tackle questions of ownership of airports and/or compensation.

Figure 4 below illustrates, conceptually, how this intervention may work, by giving part of the infrastructure generated benefit, in the form of *shares assigned to the existing properties* owned by the affected communities. In this way each property value will be topped up by the presence and economic benefit of the infrastructure and, more importantly, it will stay with the property and not with the original owner. This should mitigate the fear and perception that local affected communities are the only ones to experience a disbenefit.

Fig. 4. Scheme of shared benefits

However, there is a limit in reducing adverse noise effects by measures addressing non-acoustical contributors of community noise responses: These measures might help to reduce responses of disturbance and annoyance due to noise but they do not necessarily prevent long term health effects of higher, health-relevant noise exposures. This means that with these interventions one cannot pay off the acceptance of unhealthy living conditions.

This paper provides a comprehensive review of the identified other relevant sectors, but then from the case studies analysed some important information suitable for transferability and suggesting some good practice that can be employed in aviation have been identified.

Examples given from different transport sectors (road and rail), as well as those from other noise sources (wind park, construction, etc.) show some similarities to aviation on the steps taken to assess and manage noise impacts. They all consider monitoring, and most of them modelling and mapping before selecting mitigation measures to reduce the noise impact. Some lessons learned can be shared and explored further, illustrated in the *community engagement chapter* and in several examples of case studies presented in the Appendix.

However, the important lesson aviation needs to learn is that since population in urban areas is likely to be exposed to many noise source, the perception of noise disturbance can be very different also depending on which other sector sources are present, hence a holistic approach to reduce annoyance seems to be the best way forward, especially in urban areas.

Thus, a topic for future research should include a more holistic approach to assess noise impacts from different sectors, in an integrated and coordinated manner, since what remains essential is to reduce the annoyance and health impact due to noise, while the type of source remains important only in selecting appropriate mitigation strategies at source.

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